

Letter

Gate-voltage-dependent ionic diffusion and transient dynamics in organic electrochemical transistors

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A B S T R A C T

Organic electrochemical transistors (OECTs) exhibit transient current responses governed by the interplay between ionic motion and electronic transport in the polymer channel. In this work, transient behaviours of PEDOT:PSS OECTs are investigated under a step change in gate voltage. The gate current consistently decays exponentially across different drain biases, allowing extraction of the ionic diffusion time constant τ_d via comparison with an analytical model. In contrast, drain current transients show bias- and polarity-dependent temporal profiles, reflecting the modulation of lateral transit of electronic carriers by the drain-source potential. Despite these variations, the extracted decay constants remain consistent with those from gate-current analysis. These results demonstrate that vertical ionic diffusion predominantly determines the device's intrinsic temporal response and lateral electronic transport shapes the transient characteristics, providing a clear physical basis for interpreting time-dependent behaviours in mixed ionic–electronic conductors.

Organic electrochemical transistors (OECTs) are hybrid ionic–electronic devices in which ions from the electrolyte modulate the conductivity of a polymer channel [1–5]. Through this coupling of ionic transport and electronic conduction, OECTs operate at low voltages and exhibit high transconductance, while also displaying complex dynamical behaviours such as hysteresis, transient currents, and synaptic-like plasticity [6–10]. A predictive understanding of transient switching is essential for optimising OECT performance in sensing, bioelectronics, and neuromorphic computing [11–17].

Extensive studies have investigated OECT dynamics such as steady-state transfer and output characteristics using both experimental and modelling approaches, including equivalent circuit representations and frameworks coupling ionic diffusion with electronic transport [13, 18–25]. Their time-domain dynamics remain less systematically understood, though. Transient analysis provides a direct probe of ion transport kinetics, revealing how vertical ionic motion and lateral carrier drift collectively determine device operation. Although prior studies have typically interpreted the transient response as a combined effect of ionic and electronic processes, their individual contributions remain insufficiently resolved [26–28].

PEDOT:PSS serves as the benchmark OECT material, owing to its well-characterised ionic transport properties and widespread use in sensing and neuromorphic applications [1, 15, 18, 25, 29–32]. In our previous work, we analysed vertical ion diffusion in two-terminal PEDOT:PSS structures and identified features of anomalous diffusion

[33]. We also investigated poly(3-hexylthiophene) (P3HT)-based OECTs and established a transmission-line model that combines electronic drift with ionic diffusion [22].

Building on these foundations, we now perform systematic transient measurements on three-terminal PEDOT:PSS OECTs and interpret the results within the analytical diffusion–transport model developed by Bisquert and Tessler [23], which extends the classical Bernards-Malliaras model [18] and quantitatively captures the coupled vertical ion diffusion and lateral electronic transport processes that govern transient responses to gate-voltage steps.

Fig. 1a illustrates the device structure and electrical configuration of the OECT investigated in this study. The device features a PEDOT:PSS channel with a length of $L = 50 \mu\text{m}$, width $w = 1 \text{mm}$, and thickness $d = 200 \text{nm}$. Details of the fabrication procedure are provided in the Supporting Information. Briefly, the PEDOT:PSS channel was deposited by spin-coating a ethylene glycol-enhanced formulation with crosslinker [25].

The steady output and transfer characteristics exhibit the standard behaviour expected in depletion-mode of PEDOT:PSS OECTs (Fig. 1b and c). The output curves show the typical linear-to-saturation transition, demonstrating drain-current modulation by the gate voltage [1, 30]. The transfer characteristics in Figs. 1c and 3a, b show the same trend, along with pronounced hysteresis consistent with ionic diffusion dynamics [22, 34]. To further elucidate the origin of the hysteresis, additional sweep-rate-dependent transfer curves and step-driven

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Fig. 1. (a) Schematic of the PEDOT:PSS OEET device structure. Gold (Au) source and drain electrodes were patterned and deposited on Si/SiO₂ substrates. The gate electrode is a silver/silver chloride (Ag/AgCl) immersed in 0.1 M sodium chloride (NaCl) aqueous solution electrolyte; (b) Static output curves ($I_d - V_{ds}$) recorded at different gate voltages (0V, 0.2V, 0.4V and 0.6V); (c) Transfer curves ($I_d - V_{gs}$) obtained under different negative V_{ds} bias (−0.05 V, −0.4 V and −0.8 V) at scan rate 75 mV/s. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

measurements are provided in Fig. 4 and the Supporting Information (Fig. S9–11).

These steady-state characteristics establish the baseline electronic behaviour of the device and provide the foundation for subsequent transient analysis aimed at quantifying the timescales of ionic diffusion under dynamic gating.

Transient gate currents were recorded following a gate-voltage step, ΔV_g , under various constant drain biases V_{ds} . The gate-voltage range was chosen to ensure clear and reproducible current modulation. Within this window, the channel remains partially doped and stable, providing representative transient behaviour. As shown in Fig. 2a and b and Fig. S2, all gate current traces exhibit a pronounced initial spike followed by a gradual exponential decay. When the same ΔV_g is applied at different V_{ds} , the transient decay curves nearly overlap throughout the relaxation period. This close similarity in both amplitude and temporal shape indicates that the gate response is largely independent of drain bias, suggesting a common underlying ionic process.

To quantify these transient behaviours, we adopt the analytical diffusion–transport model proposed by Bisquert and Tessler [23] (see Supporting Information). The model defines two characteristic time-scales: First, the ionic diffusion time, τ_d ,

$$\tau_d = \frac{d^2}{D_{ion}} \quad (1)$$

determined by the film thickness d and the ions diffusion coefficient D_{ion} , which governs ion penetration into the channel through vertical insertion.

Second, the electronic transit time, τ_e , which determines lateral carrier equilibration along the channel,

$$\tau_e = \frac{L^2}{\mu_p |V_{ds}|} \quad (2)$$

The gate current decays exponentially with time follows,

$$i_g(t) = C_\mu \frac{dv_h}{dt} = \frac{C_\mu \Delta V}{\tau_d} e^{-t/\tau_d} \quad (3)$$

C_μ is the chemical (or volume) capacitance.

We first subtracted the steady-state value from each transient to remove background offsets and then plotted $\ln i_g(t)$ versus t to identify the exponential region. Since the decay follows a single-exponential form consistent with Eq. (3), the linear regression in natural logarithm scale yields slopes corresponding to $-1/\tau_d$.

At very short timescales, the gate current displays an initial spike attributed to capacitive charging at the electrolyte–channel and electrolyte–gate interfaces rather than to ionic diffusion within the polymer [1,23,35]. This non-diffusive contribution causes deviations from single-exponential behaviour during the first few milliseconds and must be excluded from the diffusion analysis. Accordingly, as shown in Fig. 2c, a minimum time of $t_{min} \sim 7.5$ ms is set to exclude the capacitive region. Linear fits are applied before the system reaches steady state. The extracted slopes (Table 1) yield τ_d values of 30.3–39.8 ms under all conditions. The comparison of the initial capacitive spike is discussed in Fig. S4

Both the visual similarity of the gate-current decays and the numerical consistency of the extracted τ_d across different V_{ds} reflect the ion diffusion process responsible for charging or discharging the film. The ion diffusion time τ_d is not sensitive to different V_{ds} , and the gate current depends solely on vertical ionic diffusion, not on lateral electronic transport.

Having established from the gate transients that the ionic diffusion process is characterized by a single, bias-independent time constant τ_d , we next analysed how the drain current evolves under identical conditions to probe the coupling between vertical ionic diffusion and horizontal electronic transport.

Under the same ΔV_g conditions, as shown in Fig. 3c and d, the drain-

Fig. 2. (a) Gate-current decays $I_g(t)$ after baseline-subtracted under different negative V_{ds} (respectively are -0.01 V, -0.05 V and -0.4 V) with a gate-voltage step $\Delta V_g = 0.2$ V from 0.3 V to 0.5 V (inset purple pulse); (b) $i_g(t)$ under different positive drain-source bias ($+0.01$ V, $+0.05$ V and $+0.4$ V); (c) $i_g(t)$ on semi-log curve with the exponential fits region (in red) yield slopes m_g . (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Table 1

Fitted slopes m_d and m_g , estimated τ_e , extracted τ_d (ms) and corresponding diffusion coefficients $D_{ion} = 4d^2/(\pi^2)\tau_d$ for all representative conditions.

θ	V_{ds}	Slope m_g (ms^{-1})	Slope m_d (ms^{-1})	τ_d (ms) from i_g	τ_d (ms) from i_d	τ_e (ms)	Regime	D_{ion} from i_g ($10^{-9} cm^2/s$)	D_{ion} from i_d ($10^{-9} cm^2/s$)
+	+0.01V	-0.030 ± 0.001	-0.044 ± 0.001	33.2	23.7	125.0	$\tau_e > \tau_d$	4.80	6.76
1									
+	+0.05V	-0.029 ± 0.001	-0.043 ± 0.002	34.5	23.3	25.0	$\tau_e \approx \tau_d$	4.64	6.88
1									
+	+0.4V	-0.025 ± 0.001	-0.032 ± 0.001	39.8	31.2	3.1	$\tau_e < \tau_d$	4.04	5.20
1									
-	-0.01V	-0.030 ± 0.001	-0.036 ± 0.001	33.3	27.8	125.0	$\tau_e > \tau_d$	4.80	5.76
1									
-	-0.05V	-0.030 ± 0.001	-0.025 ± 0.001	33.3	39.5	25.0	$\tau_e \approx \tau_d$	4.80	4.16
1									
-	-0.4V	-0.033 ± 0.001	-0.036 ± 0.001	30.3	27.8	3.1	$\tau_e < \tau_d$	5.28	5.76
1									

current transients exhibit richer dynamics than the gate current, encompassing four reproducible morphologies depending on drain polarity defined as $\theta = V_{ds}/|V_{ds}| = \pm 1$.

For $\theta = -1$, the current typically shows spike-decay-type behaviours leading to a lower steady-state current (same trend as the transfer curve in Fig. 3a.) The spike amplitude remains nearly constant from the capacitive charging spike. The initial spikes comparison is in the Supporting Information.

For $\theta = +1$, the transient exhibits either a decay or a rising response that includes a short capacitive spike. At small $|V_{ds}|$, this spike appears immediately after the gate-voltage step, whereas at higher $|V_{ds}|$ it becomes obscured by the larger steady-state current (e.g., $V_{ds} = +0.4$ V in Fig. S5a). As $|V_{ds}|$ increases, the transient gradually evolves into an exponential rise with time, approaching saturation, consistent with a drift-limited charging process.

The four types of transients in Fig. 3 are the same as the model-predicted types in Fig. S1.

In addition to the transient responses, the transfer characteristics in Fig. 3a and b and Fig. 1c exhibit a finite hysteresis, which originates from diffusion-controlled ionic dynamics. During gate-voltage sweeps, the vertical diffusion of ions governs the temporal evolution of the volumetric doping level in the channel. Because ionic redistribution across the film thickness requires finite time, the channel conductivity at a given gate voltage depends on the sweep history, resulting in the observed hysteresis. As shown in Fig. 4, step-gated measurements closely reproduce the corresponding segments of continuous transfer curves, showing consistent current magnitudes, trends, and hysteresis directions. The current curves exhibit clear sweep-rate-dependent shifts

(Fig. 4b) from slow to fast rates, directly reflecting the hysteresis observed in the transfer characteristics (Fig. 4c).

This correspondence indicates that the sweep-rate-dependent hysteresis reflects finite response dynamics rather than changes in steady-state conduction. When the gate-voltage sweep rate approaches the ionic diffusion time τ_d , diffusion-dominated capacitive behaviour and switching-like features coexist, with their relative weight determined by the sweep rate. Faster modulation highlights non-equilibrium diffusion, while the steady-state drain current is still set by the equilibrium ionic configuration. With sufficiently detailed sweep-rate data, the full transition of hysteresis from inductive to capacitive could be obtained; here, we show only a simple visualization, with corresponding supplementary data provided in the Supporting Information. These considerations establish a direct link between the observed hysteresis in transfer curves and the underlying diffusion-limited transient dynamics.

To further elucidate the mechanisms behind the observed transient dynamics, we performed a quantitative analysis using the same diffusion-transport model applied to the gate current with the expression [23],

$$i_d(t) = \left[\frac{f_B \beta_\mu}{\tau_d} + \left(\frac{\theta}{\tau_e} - \frac{f_B \beta_\mu}{\tau_d} \right) (1 - e^{-t/\tau_d}) \right] C_\mu \Delta V \quad (4)$$

where, $f_B \approx 0.5$ is a partition factor [18] and β_μ accounts for the density dependence of mobility.

The ionic diffusion time τ_d was extracted by plotting $\ln i_d(t)$ versus time after subtracting the steady-state component $I_{d,0}^s$. The linear region yields $-1/\tau_d$ as the slope m_d . Unlike the gate current, the $\ln i_d(t)$ occa-

Fig. 3. (a) Transfer curve based on situations $\theta = +1$ and (b) $\theta = -1$; Drain current transients $I_d(t)$ after a gate-voltage step of $\Delta V_g = 0.2\text{V}$ (indicated in Fig. 3a and b as green line) under (c) different negative $V_{ds} -0.01\text{ V}, -0.05\text{ V}$ and (d) under different positive $V_{ds} +0.01\text{ V}, +0.05\text{ V}$ at scan rate 75 mV/s . The series of bias $\pm 0.4\text{ V}$ is shown in Fig. S5; (e) Semi-log plots of all the baseline-subtracted I_d transients and linear fits used to extract slopes $m_d = -1/\tau_d$; fit windows are in red curve. V_{ds} respectively are $-0.01\text{ V}, -0.05\text{ V}, -0.4\text{ V}, +0.01\text{ V}, +0.05\text{ V}$ and $+0.4\text{ V}$. Whole comparisons of different conditions and the process for fitting are described in Fig. S5, S6 and S7. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

sionally deviates from perfect linearity due to lateral voltage effects; therefore, the gate current provides a cleaner and more reproducible signal for extracting τ_d with high confidence. Nevertheless, the τ_d values obtained ($\approx 23.3\text{--}39.5\text{ ms}$) remain in the same value range as those extracted from gate-current transients, confirming the reliability of this analysis.

According to Eq. (4), $i_d(t)$ can be decomposed into time-independent and time-dependent components. When τ_d is small or comparable to τ_e , the two contributions are similar, resulting in a moderate growth of the time-dependent component. When τ_d becomes large and τ_e remains small, the difference $(\theta/\tau_e - f_B\beta_\mu/\tau_d)$ increases, and strongly amplifies the time-dependent part of $i_d(t)$, leading to a change in transient types.

To further evaluate the relevant timescales, the electronic transit time τ_e was estimated according to $\tau_e = L^2 / (\mu_p |V_{ds}|)$, using a channel length $L = 50\ \mu\text{m}$ and an assumed hole mobility $\mu_p = 0.02\text{ cm}^2\text{V}^{-1}\text{s}^{-1}$. The extracted τ_d and calculated τ_e are summarised in Table 1 and plotted in Fig. 5, illustrating the crossover between ionic and electronic regimes (The comparison of τ_e with different μ_p is listed in Table S2). As $|V_{ds}|$ increases, τ_e decreases markedly while τ_d remains nearly constant.

These transient features result from the interplay between vertical ion diffusion (τ_d) and lateral electronic transit (τ_e). In the regime where $\tau_e \gg \tau_d$ (for instance, at $\theta = +1$), lateral redistribution is slower than ionic insertion, leading to a transient imbalance that may manifest as an overshoot. As $|V_{ds}|$ increases, τ_e decreases, accelerating electronic equilibration and transforming the transient from a spike decay to an exponential rise. Thus, the ratio τ_e/τ_d under varying $|V_{ds}|$ determines the observed transient type, quantitatively linking experiment and model.

The experimental classification of transients (Fig. 3) and the model framework (Fig. S1, Table S1) together confirm that OECT dynamics arise from the interplay between vertical ionic diffusion and lateral electronic transport. The invariance of τ_d across all drain biases indicates that ionic motion is purely governed by electrolyte-channel coupling, while the evolving transient shapes directly track the changing hierarchy of τ_d and τ_e .

Moreover, given a film thickness of around 200 nm , the τ_d obtained

from both analysis methods correspond to diffusion coefficients in the range of $4.04 \times 10^{-9}\text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$ to $6.88 \times 10^{-9}\text{ cm}^2/\text{s}$, consistent with literature values and our previous work [24,33,36–39]. The close numerical agreement confirms that both approaches probe the same vertical ion diffusion process and validate the use of either current for quantitative analysis of ionic dynamics.

In summary, the gate current transient response of PEDOT:PSS OECTs is governed solely by the applied gate voltage and reflects the vertical ionic diffusion process in the channel, characterized by a single time constant, ionic diffusion time, τ_d which is independent of drain-source voltage, while the drain current reflects both τ_d and τ_e . The excellent agreement between experiment and the analytical diffusion-transport model demonstrates that OECT transients can be quantitatively understood through this minimal yet robust framework. Extending this approach to other mixed ionic-electronic conductors (MIECs) and performing further quantitative analyses of τ_e will represent important directions for future work. The present results thus establish the broad applicability of the model and provide a solid foundation for interpreting switching dynamics in OECTs and related MIECs.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Heyi Zhang: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Data curation. **Juan Bisquert:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Data availability statement

The data presented here can be accessed at <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17373838> (Zenodo) under the license CC BY 4.0 (Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International).

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal

Fig. 4. Comparison between step-gated responses and continuous transfer characteristics at different effective sweep rates. (a) Stepwise gate-voltage sequences corresponding to effective sweep rates of 100 mV/s (blue) and 10 mV/s (orange); (b) Drain current as a function of gate voltage obtained from decreasing V_g sweeps, at $V_{ds} = +0.4V$, $\theta = +1$; (c) Drain-current evolution from continuous transfer curves measured at sweep rates of 50 (orange) and 100 mV/s (blue). The black arrows indicate the sweep direction. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

Fig. 5. Comparison of estimated electronic transit time τ_e and measured ionic diffusion time τ_d . Both τ_e and τ_d were plotted as a function of $|V_{ds}|$ in log-log scale, revealing a nearly $1/|V_{ds}|$ dependence of τ_e , consistent with the definition of electronic transit time.

relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Juan Bisquert reports financial support was provided by European Research Council. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.orgel.2025.107367>.

Data availability

I have put my data on Zenodo.

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